

Fixed Point Theorems in Neutrosophic Fuzzy Metric Space and a Characterization to its Completeness

Samriddhi Ghosh¹, Ramakant Bhardwaj^{2,*}, Satyendra Narayan³ and Sonam Sonam⁴

¹Department of Mathematics, Amity University Kolkata, India; ritha98@gmail.com

²Department of Mathematics, Amity University Kolkata, India; drrkbhardwaj100@gmail.com

³School of Computer Science and Technology, Algoma University, Canada; narayan.satyendra@gmail.com

⁴Department of Mathematics, Amity University Kolkata, India; sonam27msu@gmail.com

*Correspondence: drrkbhardwaj@gmail.com

Abstract. The present research work aims to establish some basic conventional fixed point theorems such as the Banach fixed point theorem, Edelstein fixed point theorem and Kannan fixed point theorem, for a recently introduced topological space, known as the neutrosophic fuzzy metric space. The Kannan fixed point theorem has also further been classified into two categories namely, $(1/2)$ –Kannan and (1) –Kannan fixed point theorems. Also the concept of semi-metric in the said space has been introduced, and along with it the results hence obtained are used to characterize the completeness of the mentioned space. To the best of known literatures, this type of work in the said space has not yet been found.

Keywords: Fixed Point (FP); Fuzzy Sets ($F_{\mathfrak{E}}$); Fuzzy Metric Space ($F_{\mathfrak{M}S}$); Neutrosophic Sets ($N_{\mathfrak{E}}$); Neutrosophic Fuzzy Sets ($N_{\mathfrak{F}S}$); Neutrosophic Fuzzy Metric Space ($NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$); Kannan Contraction (K_c).

1. Introduction

A mathematical paradigm known as $F_{\mathfrak{E}}$ theory addresses sets whose constituents have varying degrees of membership. This divergence from conventional set theory, which holds that an element either belongs to or does not belong to a set, enables more flexible and subtle modeling, especially when category borders are unclear or ambiguous. This field of research was established by [3] a groundbreaking paper, Fuzzy Sets, which was published in 1965. Since then, numerous other scientific disciplines have been impacted by this entirely new area of

inquiry. Since the introduction of $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$ in 1965, many developments have been made. In 1986, for example, [4] presented intuitionistic $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$, and in 1999, [5] proposed $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$. Also, Orthopair $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$ were introduced by [6] in 2023. The introduction of $F_{\mathfrak{MS}}$ by [7] in 1975 and its modification by [8] in 1994, intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces by [9] in 1997, and intuitionistic $F_{\mathfrak{MS}}$ by [10] in 2004 are just a few of the related concepts that have developed as a result of these foundational contributions.

Nonetheless, a FP of a function is a location that is both within the function's domain and range. It should also be noted that $h(a) = a$ if a is a FP of a function h . In other words, it is the domain element that the function maps to itself. Notably, [1] first proposed this idea in 1912. [2, 16, 18, 19, 41, 45, 47] are some noteworthy works that contributed to the development of this notion after it was established.

Numerous additional mathematical studies have been influenced by the introduction of these ideas and concepts. For example, [11] defined fuzzy metric space in 1984 as the distance between two points and expressed it as a positive fuzzy number; The concept of $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$ was introduced by [12] in 2006 as a generalization of intuitionistic $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$; [14] introduced algebraic operations like modal operators and normalization to intuitionistic $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$ in 2014; [15] investigated the practical applications of $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$ in decision-making contexts; and [13] in 2012 extended the concepts of fuzzy topological space and intuitionistic fuzzy topological space to the case of $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$. In addition to these, a number of researchers investigated other generalizations of fuzzy metric space, including bipolar fuzzy metric space, orthogonal fuzzy metric space, soft fuzzy metric space, intuitionistic fuzzy metric space, and so on [16–26, 47]. Moreover, a number of new ideas pertaining to $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$ were presented by [27], including multi-valued $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$, bipolar $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$, refined $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$, rough $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$, and rough bipolar $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$. Furthermore, [28] used $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$ in combination with multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methodologies to solve a real-world wind turbine problem.

[29] presented the idea of neutrosophic metric spaces in 2020. Furthermore, multiple fixed-point results have been developed in this extension [30] with some generalizations of $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$ by investigators, which includes orthogonal neutrosophic metric spaces in [31], neutrosophic 2-metric spaces in [32], orthogonal neutrosophic 2-metric spaces in [33], neutrosophic pentagonal metric spaces in [34], neutrosophic b-metric space in [35], then in [48] the definition of the idea of neutrosophic rectangular extended b-metric spaces and establishment of some FP findings it, [49] also proposed a theory regarding neutrosophic triplet v-generalized metric space etc. Notably, $N_{\mathfrak{S}}$ were also introduced by [36] in 2020. It is easy to see how the idea of fuzzy metric space was developed using the idea of $F_{\mathfrak{G}}$. Similarly, the concept of neutrosophic metric space has been defined by the philosophy of $N_{\mathfrak{G}}$. Given these considerations, the main goal

of this study is to clarify the idea behind $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$. For this, the idea of $N_{\mathfrak{S}S}$ has been applied, much like previously mentioned.

More recently, Ghosh et al. [44] introduced $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ (NFMS), a mathematical framework that more closely reflects the complex and uncertain nature of real-world phenomena like medical diagnosis, decision-making under ambiguity, or identifying trends in ambiguous data sets. This encourages the creation of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ theory in order to improve the models, analyses, and decision-making capabilities in uncertain contexts. FP theorems pertaining to $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ are a very new area of study, and virtually no other mathematician has investigated them. The Banach, Edelstein, and Kannan FP theorems are established in light of the $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ in order to close this gap.

The potential of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ to more precisely represent uncertainty and indeterminacy in real-world occurrences than conventional fuzzy or crisp sets is what inspired their introduction. $N_{\mathfrak{S}}$ offer a more complex explanation of uncertainty by enabling the representation of elements with three components: truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood. The field of medical diagnosis could serve as an illustration of the necessity of NFMS. Imagine a situation in which a patient exhibits symptoms that are not exclusively suggestive of one illness. On a scale from 0 to 1, traditional $F_{\mathfrak{S}}$ could depict the patient's probability of getting a certain illness. However, if the symptoms are unclear or contradictory, this method might not fully convey the doubt around the diagnosis. Neutrosophic sets, on the other hand, can more fully capture the uncertainty by explicitly taking into consideration the degree of truth, indeterminacy, and falsehood connected to every symptom and possible diagnosis. Then, using $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$, a metric space may be defined in which the distance between two diagnoses indicates both how similar they are and how ambiguous or indeterminate each one is.

The paper's structure is described as follows. Section 2 presents the basic concepts of $N_{\mathfrak{S}S}$, $F_{\mathfrak{M}S}$, and $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$. A few FP theorems in $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ are established in Section 3. Finally, the conclusion is included in Section 4 of this work. Additionally, this research can be expanded to examine $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ in relation to other ideas like approximation theory, optimization theory, best proximity point results, etc. Furthermore, the established theory and results can be linked to ideas such as generalized metric spaces, soft sets, soft equality, soft lattices, etc. [37,38,45,46].

2. Preliminaries

To establish the main outcomes the hypothesis are considered as follows:

Theorem 2.1. [2] *Every contraction mapping on a complete metric space possesses a unique FP.*

Definition 2.2. ($F_{\mathfrak{E}}$) [3, 7, 10] A $F_{\mathfrak{E}}$ \mathfrak{F} in an universal set X is defined as

$$\mathfrak{F} = \{ \langle \rho, \mu_{\mathfrak{F}}(\rho) \rangle : 0 \leq \mu_{\mathfrak{F}}(\rho) \leq 1, \rho \in X \}.$$

In this context, $\mu_{\mathfrak{F}}(\rho)$ is also known as the membership grade of ρ in \mathfrak{F} .

Definition 2.3. ($N_{\mathfrak{E}}$) [5, 29] A $N_{\mathfrak{E}}$ \mathfrak{N} in an universal set X is defined as

$\mathfrak{N} = \{ \langle \rho, (T_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), I_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), F_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho)) \rangle : \rho \in X, T_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), I_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), F_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho) \in]0^-, 1^+[\}$. In this context, $T_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), I_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho), F_{\mathfrak{N}}(\rho)$ are the notations for truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership grades of ρ in \mathfrak{N} respectively. Here, $]0^-, 1^+[$ is another way of representing $[0, 1]$ under the purview of neutrosophic logic.

Definition 2.4. ($N_{\mathfrak{F}S}$) [36, 44] The definition of a $N_{\mathfrak{F}S}$ \mathfrak{B} in a universal set X is given as,

$$\mathfrak{B} = \{ \langle \rho, (\mu_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho), T_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), I_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), F_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu)) \rangle : \rho \in X, \mu_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho) \in [0, 1], \\ T_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), I_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), F_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu) \in]0^-, 1^+[\}$$

In this context, each membership grade $\mu_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho)$ is expressed by a truth, indeterminacy and falsity membership grade denoted by $T_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), I_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu)$ and $F_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu)$ respectively.

Definition 2.5. [7, 8, 29] A function $\star : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a continuous t -norm (TN) if it satisfies the following conditions, for any $a, b, c, d \in [0, 1]$:

- (1) $a \star 1 = a$,
- (2) If $a \leq b$ and $c \leq d$, then $a \star c \leq b \star d$,
- (3) \star is continuous,
- (4) \star is commutative and associative.

Definition 2.6. [7, 8, 29] A function $\diamond : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a continuous t -conorm (TC) if it satisfies the following conditions, for any $a, b, c, d \in [0, 1]$:

- (1) $a \star 0 = a$,
- (2) If $a \leq b$ and $c \leq d$, then $a \star c \leq b \star d$,
- (3) \star is continuous,
- (4) \star is commutative and associative.

Definition 2.7. ($F_{\mathfrak{M}S}$) [7, 47] A 3-tuple (G, \mathfrak{S}, \star) is said to be a fuzzy metric space if G is a non empty arbitrary set, \star is a continuous t -norm and \mathfrak{S} is a $F_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on $G^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions, for any $\rho, \sigma, w \in G$ and $s, \kappa > 0$

- (1) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 0$,
- (2) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ iff $\rho = \sigma$,
- (3) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \rho, \kappa)$,
- (4) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \star \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, w, s) \leq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, w, \kappa + s)$,
- (5) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Definition 2.8. ($NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$) [44] A $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ (NFMS) is a seven-tuple $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$, given G is an arbitrary set, \star a continuous t -norm, \diamond a continuous t -conorm and $\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}$ are $F_{\mathfrak{S}}$ on $G^2 \times (0, \infty)$ which are analogous to the notations $\mu(\rho), T_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu), I_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu)$ and $F_{\mathfrak{B}}(\rho, \mu)$ in Definition 2.3 satisfying the following conditions, for any $\rho, \sigma, w \in G$ and $s, \kappa > 0$,

- (1) $0 \leq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1, 0 \leq \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1, 0 \leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1, 0 \leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1,$
- (2) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) + \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) + \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) + \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 4,$
- (3) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \rho, \kappa),$
- (4) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ iff $\rho = \sigma,$
- (5) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1,$
- (6) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \star \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, w, s) \leq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, z, \kappa + s),$
- (7) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\} \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous,
- (8) $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \rho, \kappa),$
- (9) $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ iff $\rho = \sigma,$
- (10) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1,$
- (11) $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \star \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, w, s) \leq \mathfrak{A}(\rho, z, \kappa + s),$
- (12) $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\} \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous,
- (13) $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \rho, \kappa),$
- (14) $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0$ iff $\rho = \sigma,$
- (15) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0,$
- (16) $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, w, s) \geq \mathfrak{M}(\rho, z, \kappa + s),$
- (17) $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\} \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous,
- (18) $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \rho, \kappa),$
- (19) $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0$ iff $\rho = \sigma,$
- (20) $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0,$
- (21) $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, w, s) \geq \mathfrak{R}(\rho, z, \kappa + s),$
- (22) $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot) : \mathbb{R}^+ \cup \{0\} \rightarrow (0, 1]$ is continuous,
- (23) $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0, \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0, \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ and $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ if $\kappa \leq 0.$

Here, the certainty that the distance between ρ and σ is smaller than t is represented by $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa)$, while the degrees of nearness, neutrality, and non-nearness of σ and σ with regard to t are represented by $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa),$ and $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa),$ respectively.

Remark 2.9. From the above definition, it is clear that, for any $\rho, \sigma \in G,$ $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot)$ and $\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot)$ are non-decreasing functions on $[0, \infty),$ and on the other hand, $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot)$ and $\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot)$ are non-increasing functions on $[0, \infty).$

Remark 2.10. It can be concluded easily from Remark 2.9 that, given $\rho, \sigma \in G,$ if $\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \kappa$ and $\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) < \kappa \forall \kappa \in (0, \infty),$ then $\rho = \sigma.$

Every neutrosophic fuzzy metric $(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ on a set G induces a metrizable topology $\tau_{(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R})}$ on G which has the family of open sets $\{O(\rho, \epsilon, \kappa) : \rho \in G, \epsilon \in (0, 1), \kappa \in (0, \infty)\}$ as its base, where for any $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$ and $\kappa > 0$,

$$O(\rho, \epsilon, \kappa) = \{\sigma \in G : \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon, \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \epsilon, \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) < \epsilon, \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) < \epsilon\}.$$

Definition 2.11. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$.

(a) A sequence $\{\rho_n\} \in G$ is known to be a Cauchy sequence if for each $t, \alpha > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) = 1 \text{ and,} \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(b) A sequence $\{\rho_n\} \in G$ is convergent to some $\rho \in G$ if $\forall \kappa > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho, \kappa) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho, \kappa) = 1 \text{ and,} \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho, \kappa) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho, \kappa) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

(The limit may be uniquely ascertained from the specifications (6), (11), (16), and (21) in Definition 2.8, since \star and \diamond are continuous.)

A $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ is considered compact if every sequence contains a convergent subsequence, and complete if and only if every Cauchy sequence is convergent.

We now go over a crucial example involving $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ that will be utilized later, in the last part of the study.

Example 2.12. Let (G, d) be a metric space. Specify the functions,

$$\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d : G \times G \times (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ as,}$$

- (1) $\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ if $d(\rho, \sigma) < \kappa$,
- (2) $\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0$ if $d(\rho, \sigma) \geq \kappa$,
- (3) $\mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 0$ if $d(\rho, \sigma) < \kappa$,
- (4) $\mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) = 1$ if $d(\rho, \sigma) \geq \kappa$.

Then, for any continuous t-norm and t-conorm, \star and \diamond , respectively, $(\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ is a neutrosophic fuzzy metric on G such that the topologies induced by d and $(\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ coincide. Additionally, if (G, d) is complete, then it can be said that $(\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ is also complete.

Definition 2.13. [39] A semi-metric for a topological space (X, τ) is a function denoted as $d : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$, satisfying the following conditions $\forall \rho, \sigma \in X$ and $\mathfrak{A} \subset X$,

- (1) $d(\rho, \sigma) = 0 \iff \rho = \sigma$,
- (2) $d(\rho, \sigma) = d(\sigma, \rho)$,
- (3) $\rho \in \bar{\mathfrak{A}} \iff d(\rho, \mathfrak{A}) = 0$.

Definition 2.14. [39] Let (X, \mathfrak{S}, \star) be a fuzzy metric space. For each $\rho, \sigma \in X$, take $d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho, \sigma) = \sup \{\kappa \geq 0 : \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1 - \kappa\}$. Then $d_{\mathfrak{S}}$ is a semi-metric for $(X, \tau_{\mathfrak{S}})$, satisfying $d_{\mathfrak{S}} \leq 1$ and $d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho, \sigma) < \kappa \iff \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \kappa \forall \kappa > 0$. Therefore a sequence in X is a Cauchy sequence for $d_{\mathfrak{S}}$ iff it is a Cauchy sequence in (X, \mathfrak{S}, \star) .

Theorem 2.15. ($K_{\mathfrak{C}}$)(Kannan [41]) Let (G, d) be a complete metric space and $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ be a mapping such that there exists a constant $c \in (0, 1/2)$ that satisfies, $\forall \rho, \sigma \in G$,

$$d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) \leq c[d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho) + d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma)], \forall \rho, \sigma \in G.$$

Then \mathfrak{F} has an unique FP.

Theorem 2.16. (Reich [42], Subrahmanyam [43]) A metric space (G, d) is complete iff every $K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G has a FP.

Definition 2.17. [39] Let (G, \mathfrak{S}, \star) be a fuzzy metric space. Then a mapping $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ is a $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G if,

$$\min \{\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa)\} > 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa$$

for some $c \in (0, 1)$, $\forall \kappa > 0$ and $\rho, \sigma \in G$.

Definition 2.18. [39] Let (G, \mathfrak{S}, \star) be a fuzzy metric space. Then a mapping $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ is a $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G if,

$$\min \{\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa)\} > 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa$$

for some $c \in (0, 1/2)$, $\forall \kappa > 0$ and $\rho, \sigma \in G$.

3. Main results

As the first result of the study, we present Banach type FP theorem in a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$. Let $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ be a mapping that satisfies,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \lambda\kappa) \geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \lambda\kappa) \geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa),$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \lambda\kappa) \leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \lambda\kappa) \leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa),$$

for any $\rho, \sigma \in G$ and $\lambda \in (0, 1)$. Then F has an unique FP.

Proof. Let $\rho \in G$ and $\rho_n = \mathfrak{F}^n \rho$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$). By simple induction it can be written that,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\lambda^n), \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\lambda^n),$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\lambda^n), \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\lambda^n),$$

for any $n, \kappa > 0$. Thus using the above relations, for any positive integer α it is obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa/\alpha) \star \dots \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n+\alpha-1}, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa/\alpha) \geq \\ &\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^n) \star \dots \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^{n+\alpha-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa/\alpha) \star \dots \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n+\alpha-1}, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa/\alpha) \geq \\ &\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^n) \star \dots \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^{n+\alpha-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa/\alpha) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n+\alpha-1}, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa/\alpha) \leq \\ &\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^n) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^{n+\alpha-1}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa/\alpha) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n+\alpha-1}, \rho_{n+\alpha}, \kappa/\alpha) \leq \\ &\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^n) \diamond \dots \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \rho_1, \kappa/\alpha\lambda^{n+\alpha-1}) \end{aligned}$$

Using (5), (10), (15) and (20) from Definition 2.8, it follows that,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) \geq \underbrace{1 \star \dots \star 1}_{\alpha \text{ times}} = 1,$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) \geq \underbrace{1 \star \dots \star 1}_{\alpha \text{ times}} = 1,$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) \leq \underbrace{0 \diamond \dots \diamond 0}_{\alpha \text{ times}} = 0,$$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n+\alpha}, \rho_n, \kappa) \leq \underbrace{0 \diamond \dots \diamond 0}_{\alpha \text{ times}} = 0.$$

That is, $\{\rho_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence, and hence convergent. Let the limit be σ . Thus by (6), (11), (16) and (21) from Definition 2.8, it follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \geq \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2\lambda}) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \rightarrow 1 \star 1 = 1, \\ \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \geq \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2\lambda}) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \rightarrow 1 \star 1 = 1, \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \leq \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2\lambda}) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \rightarrow 0 \diamond 0 = 0, \\ \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \leq \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \rho_n, \frac{\kappa}{2\lambda}) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n+1}, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{2}) \rightarrow 0 \diamond 0 = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Now by using (4), (9), (14) and (19) from Definition 2.8, it is clear that, $\mathfrak{F}\sigma = \sigma$.

Hence σ is a FP of \mathfrak{F} .

For establishing uniqueness, let $\mathfrak{F}w = w$ for some $w \in G$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &\geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) = \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) \geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^2}) \geq \dots \geq \\ &\mathfrak{S}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^n}) \rightarrow 1, \\ 1 &\geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) = \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) \geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^2}) \geq \dots \geq \\ &\mathfrak{A}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^n}) \rightarrow 1, \\ 0 &\leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) = \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) \leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^2}) \leq \dots \leq \\ &\mathfrak{M}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^n}) \rightarrow 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$0 \leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) = \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha}) \leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^2}) \leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \sigma, \frac{\kappa}{\alpha^n}) \rightarrow 0,$$

as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Therefore by (4), (9), (14) and (19) from Definition 2.8, it follows that, $\sigma = w$. Hence the FP is unique. \square

Lemma 3.2. *If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \rho_n = x$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_n = \sigma$, then $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$ and $\epsilon \in (0, \kappa)$,*

$$\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa),$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa).$$

Proof. By (6), (11), (16) and (21) in Definition 2.8, it can be deduced that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \sigma_n, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \sigma_n, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \sigma_n, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \sigma_n, \frac{\epsilon}{2}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\geq 1 \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \star 1 = \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon), \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\geq 1 \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \star 1 = \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon), \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\leq 0 \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \diamond 0 = \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon), \\ \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) &\leq 0 \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon) \diamond 0 = \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon), \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon),$$

and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon), \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa - \epsilon).$$

This completes the proof. \square

Lemma 3.3. *If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \rho_n = x$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_n = \sigma$, then $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$ and $\epsilon \in (0, \kappa)$,*

$$\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa),$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa).$$

Proof. By (6), (11), (16) and (21) in Definition 2.8, it can be deduced that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, t + \epsilon) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \star \mathfrak{S}(\sigma_n, \sigma, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, t + \epsilon) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \star \mathfrak{A}(\sigma_n, \sigma, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, t + \epsilon) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\sigma_n, \sigma, \frac{\epsilon}{2}), \\ \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, t + \epsilon) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, x, \frac{\epsilon}{2}) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\sigma_n, \sigma, \frac{\epsilon}{2}). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) &\geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, t + \epsilon) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 3.4. *If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \rho_n = \rho$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_n = \sigma$, then $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) &\geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.5. *If $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \rho_n = \rho$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sigma_n = \sigma$, then $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) &\geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) &\leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \inf \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \sigma_n, \kappa). \end{aligned}$$

Next, as the second result of the study, we present Edelstein type FP theorem in compact $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$.

Theorem 3.6. *The compact $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}} (G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ is considered. Additionally, let $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ be a mapping that fulfills,*

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &> \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) > \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &< \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) < \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \cdot). \end{aligned}$$

for any $\rho, \sigma \in G$ and $\rho \neq \sigma$. Then F possesses a FP, that is unique.

Proof. Let $\rho \in G$ and $\rho_n = \mathfrak{F}^n \rho$ ($n \in \mathbb{N}$). Suppose $\rho_n \neq \rho_{n+1} \forall n$ (else, $\mathfrak{F}\rho_n = \rho_n$). As a result, $\rho_n \neq \rho_m$ ($n \neq m$). Or else, for $m > n$ it is obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot) &= \mathfrak{S}(\rho_m, \rho_{m+1}, \cdot) > \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{m-1}, \rho_m, \cdot) > \dots > \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot), \\ \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot) &= \mathfrak{A}(\rho_m, \rho_{m+1}, \cdot) > \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{m-1}, \rho_m, \cdot) > \dots > \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot), \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot) &= \mathfrak{M}(\rho_m, \rho_{m+1}, \cdot) < \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{m-1}, \rho_m, \cdot) < \dots < \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot), \\ \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot) &= \mathfrak{R}(\rho_m, \rho_{m+1}, \cdot) < \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{m-1}, \rho_m, \cdot) < \dots < \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \cdot). \end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction. Now as G is compact, there exists a convergent subsequence $\{\rho_{n_i}\}$, for every sequence $\{\rho_n\} \in G$. Let $\lim_i \rho_{n_i} = \sigma$. And suppose $\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma \notin \{\rho_{n_i} : i \in \mathbb{N}\}$ (if it is not the case, a subsequence with such a property has to be chosen).

In accordance with the assumptions above, it can now be written that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &> \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) > \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \cdot), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &< \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) < \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \cdot). \end{aligned}$$

for any $i \in \mathbb{N}$. Then by Corollary 3.4, for any $\kappa \in (0, \infty)$ it can be obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \lim \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\geq \lim \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) = 1, \\ \lim \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\geq \lim \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) = 1, \\ \lim \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\leq \lim \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) = 0, \\ \lim \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\leq \lim \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \sigma, \kappa) = \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \sigma, \kappa) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\lim \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i} = \mathfrak{F}\sigma.$$

Similarly it can be obtained that,

$$\lim \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i} = \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma.$$

(Recollect that $\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i} = \mathfrak{F}\sigma \forall i \in \mathbb{N}$). Now $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$ it is noted that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \leq \dots \leq 1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \dots \leq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \leq \dots \leq 1, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \dots \geq \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \dots \geq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \geq \dots \geq 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \dots \geq \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \dots \geq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_{i+1}}, \kappa) \geq \dots \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\{\mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$, $\{\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$ and $\{\mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa)\}$ are all convergent to a common limit. Thus, by applying Corollary 3.4 and Corollary 3.5 to the above noted inequalities, it is obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\geq \limsup \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) = \limsup \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \liminf \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \kappa), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\geq \limsup \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) = \limsup \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \geq \liminf \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \kappa), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\leq \liminf \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) = \liminf \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \limsup \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \kappa), \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) &\leq \liminf \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) = \liminf \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \leq \limsup \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho_{n_i}, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho_{n_i}, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \kappa). \end{aligned}$$

$\forall \kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+$. Now let $y \neq \mathfrak{F}\sigma$. So, using (3.1) it can be claimed that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &< \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) < \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \cdot), \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) &> \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \cdot), \quad \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \cdot) > \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, \cdot). \end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction. This is due to the fact that \mathfrak{S} and \mathfrak{A} are left continuous and non decreasing, and \mathfrak{M} and \mathfrak{R} are right continuous and non increasing.

Hence, $\sigma = \mathfrak{F}\sigma$ is a FP of \mathfrak{F} . Uniqueness is immediate from (3.1). \square

We now extend Romaguera’s notion of Kannan type contractions for fuzzy metric space under the framework of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}_S}$, which is presented as follows, utilizing Definitions 2.17 and 2.18.

Definition 3.7. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a $NF_{\mathfrak{M}_S}$. Then a mapping $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ is a (1)– $K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G if,

$$\begin{aligned} \min \{ \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \min \{ \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa \implies \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) < c\kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa \implies \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) < c\kappa, \end{aligned}$$

for some $c \in (0, 1)$, $\forall \kappa > 0$ and $\rho, \sigma \in G$.

Definition 3.8. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$. Then a mapping $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ is a $(1/2)-K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on G if,

$$\min \{ \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} > 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa,$$

$$\min \{ \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} > 1 - \kappa \implies \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) > 1 - c\kappa,$$

$$\max \{ \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} < \kappa \implies \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) < c\kappa,$$

$$\max \{ \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} < \kappa \implies \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) < c\kappa,$$

for some $c \in (0, 1/2)$, $\forall \kappa > 0$ and $\rho, \sigma \in G$.

Theorem 3.9. *There is a FP for each $(1)-K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$.*

Proof. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$, and

$\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ be a $(1)-K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on G . Then $\exists c \in (0, 1)$ such that all the conditions in Definition 3.7 are satisfied.

Take $\kappa_0 > 1$. Then $\forall \rho, \sigma \in G$ it can be obtained that,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0) > 1 - \kappa_0 \text{ and } \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa_0) > 1 - \kappa_0,$$

$$\mathfrak{A}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0) > 1 - \kappa_0 \text{ and } \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa_0) > 1 - \kappa_0,$$

$$\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0) < \kappa_0 \text{ and } \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa_0) < \kappa_0,$$

$$\mathfrak{R}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0) < \kappa_0 \text{ and } \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa_0) < \kappa_0.$$

So by Definition 3.7, it can be written that,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa_0) > 1 - c\kappa_0,$$

$$\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa_0) < c\kappa_0.$$

From,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, F^2\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, F^2\rho, \kappa_0) > 1 - \kappa_0,$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, F^2\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, F^2\rho, \kappa_0) < \kappa_0,$$

it can be deduced that,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho, c\kappa_0) > 1 - c\kappa_0,$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}^2\rho, c\kappa_0) < c\kappa_0.$$

And similarly,

$$\mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, c\kappa_0) > 1 - c\kappa_0,$$

and

$$\mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, c\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}^2\sigma, c\kappa_0) < c\kappa_0.$$

Thus, by Definition 3.7 it is inferred that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}^2 \rho, \mathfrak{F}^2 \sigma, c^2 \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}^2 \rho, \mathfrak{F}^2 \sigma, c^2 \kappa_0) &> 1 - c^2 \kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}^2 \rho, \mathfrak{F}^2 \sigma, c^2 \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}^2 \rho, \mathfrak{F}^2 \sigma, c^2 \kappa_0) &< c^2 \kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Continuing in this way, $\forall n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho, \mathfrak{F}^n \sigma, c^n \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho, \mathfrak{F}^n \sigma, c^n \kappa_0) &> 1 - c^n \kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho, \mathfrak{F}^n \sigma, c^n \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho, \mathfrak{F}^n \sigma, c^n \kappa_0) &< c^n \kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Now fix an $\rho_0 \in G$. Define $\rho_n := \mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0 \forall n \in \mathbb{N}$. It is to be shown that $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$.

Certainly, given $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+$ and $\epsilon \in (0, 1)$, $\exists n_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $c^n \kappa_0 < \min\{\epsilon, \kappa\} \forall n \geq n_\epsilon$. Now let $m, n \geq n_\epsilon$ and $m > n$. Then, $m = n + k$ for some $k \in \mathbb{N}$, and therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_m, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, c^n \kappa_0) \\ &> 1 - c^n \kappa_0 > 1 - \epsilon, \\ \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_m, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, \kappa) \\ &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, c^n \kappa_0) \\ &> 1 - c^n \kappa_0 > 1 - \epsilon, \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_m, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, c^n \kappa_0) \\ &< c^n \kappa_0 < \epsilon, \\ \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_m, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, \kappa) \\ &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}^n \rho_0, \mathfrak{F}^n \mathfrak{F}^k \rho_0, c^n \kappa_0) \\ &< c^n \kappa_0 < \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a Cauchy sequence in $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$. So, $\exists z \in G$ such that $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow z$ in $\tau(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R})$.

It is now necessary to demonstrate that w is a FP of \mathfrak{F} . (A number of details need to be confirmed because the proof is not instantaneous.)

Choose $r, s > 0$ such that $c < s < r < 1$.

By applying induction, in the first step it has to be shown that, $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}$, (3.2)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k \kappa_0) &\geq 1 - r^k \kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k \kappa_0) \leq r^k \kappa_0.$$

Without losing generality suppose $r^k \kappa_0 \leq 1 \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$. Or else inequality (3.2) is satisfied trivially.

Now for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ define,

$$T_{k,r,s} := \{\epsilon \in (0, 1) : \epsilon + sr^{k-1} \kappa_0 < r^k \kappa_0\}.$$

Assume $k = 1$. Then it is obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa_0) &> 1 - \kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa_0) &> 1 - \kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa_0) &< \kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, \kappa_0) &< \kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

So by Remark 2.9 and Definition 3.7, it can be written that, $\forall n \in \mathbb{W}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, s\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, c\kappa_0) > 1 - c\kappa_0 > 1 - s\kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, s\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, c\kappa_0) > 1 - c\kappa_0 > 1 - s\kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, s\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, c\kappa_0) < c\kappa_0 < s\kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, s\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, c\kappa_0) < c\kappa_0 < s\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \rightarrow z$, for any $\epsilon \in T_{1,r,s} \exists n_\epsilon \in \mathbb{N}$ for which $\mathfrak{S}(w, \rho_n, \epsilon), \mathfrak{A}(w, \rho_n, \epsilon) > 1 - \epsilon$ and $\mathfrak{M}(w, \rho_n, \epsilon), \mathfrak{R}(w, \rho_n, \epsilon) < \epsilon$. As a result,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, s\kappa_0) \\ &\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - s\kappa_0) \\ &\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - r\kappa_0), \\ \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, s\kappa_0) \\ &\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - s\kappa_0) \\ &\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - r\kappa_0), \\ \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, s\kappa_0) \\ &\leq \epsilon \diamond s\kappa_0 \\ &\leq \epsilon \diamond r\kappa_0, \\ \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, s\kappa_0) \\ &\leq \epsilon \diamond s\kappa_0 \\ &\leq \epsilon \diamond r\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Taking limit as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, by continuity of \star and \diamond it can be deduced that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\geq 1 - r\kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r\kappa_0) &\leq r\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Now it is to be shown that, if inequality (3.2) holds for $k = j$, then it also holds for $k = j + 1$ (where $j \in \mathbb{N}$).

Putting $k = j$ in inequality (3.2) it is obtained that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^j\kappa_0) &> 1 - r^j\kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^j\kappa_0) &< r^j\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, since $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is Cauchy, $\exists n_j \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\forall n \geq n_j$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, r^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, r^j\kappa_0) &> 1 - r^j\kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, r^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\rho_n, \rho_{n+1}, r^j\kappa_0) &< r^j\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Then by Definition 3.7, it can be said that $\forall n \geq n_j$, (3.3)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, cr^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, cr^j\kappa_0) &> 1 - cr^j\kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, cr^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, cr^j\kappa_0) &< cr^j\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

Since $s > c$, using inequality (3.3) it can be written that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, sr^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, sr^j\kappa_0) &> 1 - sr^j\kappa_0, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, sr^j\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \rho_{n+1}, sr^j\kappa_0) &< sr^j\kappa_0. \end{aligned}$$

$\forall n \geq n_j$. Now let $\epsilon \in T_{j+1, r, s}$. Then $\epsilon + sr^j\kappa_0 < r^{j+1}\kappa_0$ and $\exists n_\epsilon > n_j$ such that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon), \mathfrak{A}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) &> 1 - \epsilon, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon), \mathfrak{R}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) &< \epsilon. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{S}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - r^{j+1}\kappa_0), \\
\mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \star \mathfrak{A}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\geq (1 - \epsilon) \star (1 - r^{j+1}\kappa_0), \\
\mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{M}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\leq \epsilon \diamond sr^j\kappa_0 \\
&\leq \epsilon \diamond r^{j+1}\kappa_0, \\
\mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \rho_{n_\epsilon}, \epsilon) \diamond \mathfrak{R}(\rho_{n_\epsilon}, \mathfrak{F}w, sr^j\kappa_0) \\
&\leq \epsilon \diamond sr^j\kappa_0 \\
&\leq \epsilon \diamond r^{j+1}\kappa_0.
\end{aligned}$$

Taking limit as $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, by the continuity of \star and \diamond it follows that,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0), \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\geq 1 - r^{j+1}\kappa_0, \\
&\text{and} \\
\mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0), \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^{j+1}\kappa_0) &\leq r^{j+1}\kappa_0.
\end{aligned}$$

Thus inequality (3.2) also holds for $k = j + 1$.

Now given $\kappa \in (0, \infty)$, $\exists k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $r^k\kappa_0 < \kappa$. So,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k\kappa_0) > 1 - r^k\kappa_0 > 1 - \kappa, \\
\mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) &\geq \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k\kappa_0) > 1 - r^k\kappa_0 > 1 - \kappa, \\
\mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k\kappa_0) < r^k\kappa_0 < \kappa, \\
\mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) &\leq \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, r^k\kappa_0) < r^k\kappa_0 < \kappa.
\end{aligned}$$

By applying Remark 2.10 here, it follows that,

$$w = \mathfrak{F}w.$$

For uniqueness let $u \in G$ such that $u = \mathfrak{F}u$. Then $\forall \kappa \in (0, \infty)$,

$$\begin{aligned}
\min \{ \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(u, \mathfrak{F}u, \kappa) \} &= 1, \\
\min \{ \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(u, \mathfrak{F}u, \kappa) \} &= 1, \\
\max \{ \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}(u, \mathfrak{F}u, \kappa) \} &= 0, \\
\max \{ \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(u, \mathfrak{F}u, \kappa) \} &= 0.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence by Definition 3.7,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}u, c\kappa), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}u, c\kappa) &> 1 - c\kappa, \\ &\text{and} \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}u, c\kappa), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}w, \mathfrak{F}u, c\kappa) &< c\kappa. \end{aligned}$$

for any $\kappa > 0$. Implies that, $\mathfrak{F}w = \mathfrak{F}u$ or, $w = u$. This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 3.10. *There is a unique FP for each $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$.*

Now we are going to discuss an example of $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ for $c = 3/5$, which is not a $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$. Indeed, it will also provide a case where Theorem 3.9 can be applied, but not Corollary 3.10.

Example 3.11. Let $G = [0, 9/5]$, and d be the typical metric on G . Then it is evident that, $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ is a complete $NF_{\mathfrak{MS}}$, where \star and \diamond stands for minimum and maximum operators respectively.

Define $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ as $\mathfrak{F}\rho = 0 \forall \rho \in [0, 6/5]$ and $\mathfrak{F}\rho = \rho/3 \forall \rho \in (6/5, 9/5]$.

Now it has to be established that F is not a $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$.

Take $c \in (0, 1/2)$. Choose $\rho = 0, y = 9/5$ and $t = 3/5c$. Then $\kappa > 1$. So,

$$\begin{aligned} \min \{ \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \min \{ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa. \end{aligned}$$

However,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(0, 3/5, 3/5) = 0 < 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(0, 3/5, 3/5) = 0 < 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(0, 3/5, 3/5) = 1 > c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(0, 3/5, 3/5) = 1 > c\kappa. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, F is not a $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G. It now remains to prove that, F is a $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ for $c = 1/2$.

To put an end to this, three cases are to be distinguished for any $\rho, \sigma \in G$.

Case 1: $\rho, \sigma \in [0, 6/5]$. Then for any $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+$,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(0, 0, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(0, 0, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(0, 0, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(0, 0, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, it meets every requirement given in Definition 3.7.

Case 2: $\rho \in [0, 6/5], y \in (6/5, 9/5]$. Then if $\kappa > 1$, it can be written that,

$$\sigma/3 \leq 3/5 < 3\kappa/5.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa.\end{aligned}$$

And hence, all the conditions in Definition 3.7 are satisfied.

Now take $\kappa \leq 1$ and suppose,

$$\begin{aligned}\min \{ \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \min \{ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa.\end{aligned}$$

Then it follows that,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, 0, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, 0, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, 0, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 0, \\ \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\rho, 0, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 0.\end{aligned}$$

As a result, $\rho < \kappa$ and $2\sigma/3 < \kappa$. This indicates that,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(0, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa.\end{aligned}$$

Therefore, all the conditions stated in Definition 3.7 are satisfied.

Case 3: $\rho, \sigma \in (6/5, 9/5]$. Without sacrificing generality, assume $\rho > \sigma$.

Now for $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}^+ - (0, 1]$, it is attainable that,

$$(\rho - y)/3 < \rho/3 \leq 3/5 < 3\kappa/5.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{N}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, all the requirements of Definition 3.7 are met.

At this point, taking $\kappa \leq 1$ and,

$$\begin{aligned}\min \{ \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \min \{ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa,\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \max \{ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa) \} &< \kappa. \end{aligned}$$

It follows that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \rho/3, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \rho/3, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \rho/3, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 0, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho, \rho/3, \kappa) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\sigma, \sigma/3, \kappa) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

As a result, $2\rho/3 < \kappa$ and $2\sigma/3 < \kappa$. Thus,

$$(\rho - \sigma)/3 < \rho/3 < \kappa/2 < 3\kappa/5.$$

This indicates that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 1 > 1 - c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c\kappa) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho/3, \sigma/3, 3\kappa/5) = 0 < c\kappa. \end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathfrak{F} is a $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$, as well as a $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on G .

Remark 3.12. Although the opposite is not always true, it may be inferred from the example above that every $(1/2) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ is also a $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$.

Remark 3.13. For all $k \in (0, 1)$, every $(k) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ will be a $(1) - K_{\mathfrak{E}}$, but the converse may not always be true. This can be shown by a similar methodology as in Example 3.11.

We now introduce the notion of semi-metric in $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ and present a characterisation of the space's completeness based on Definition 2.14.

Definition 3.14. Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$. For each $\rho, \sigma \in G$ take,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho, \sigma) &= \sup \{ \kappa \geq 0 : \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1 - \kappa \}, \\ d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho, \sigma) &= \sup \{ \kappa \geq 0 : \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \leq 1 - \kappa \}, \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho, \sigma) &= \inf \{ \kappa \leq 1 : \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \geq \kappa \}, \\ d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho, \sigma) &= \inf \{ \kappa \leq 1 : \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) \geq \kappa \}. \end{aligned}$$

Then $(d_{\mathfrak{S}}, d_{\mathfrak{A}}, d_{\mathfrak{M}}, d_{\mathfrak{R}})$ is semi-metric for $(G, \tau_{(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R})})$ if it satisfies,

- (1) $d_{\mathfrak{S}} \leq 1$ and $d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho, \sigma) < \kappa \iff \mathfrak{S}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \kappa \forall \kappa > 0$,
- (2) $d_{\mathfrak{A}} \leq 1$ and $d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho, \sigma) < \kappa \iff \mathfrak{A}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) > 1 - \kappa \forall \kappa > 0$,
- (3) $d_{\mathfrak{M}} \geq 0$ and $d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho, \sigma) > 1 - \kappa \iff \mathfrak{M}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) < \kappa \forall \kappa > 0$,
- (4) $d_{\mathfrak{R}} \geq 0$ and $d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho, \sigma) > 1 - \kappa \iff \mathfrak{R}(\rho, \sigma, \kappa) < \kappa \forall \kappa > 0$.

Consequently, if and only if a sequence in G is a Cauchy sequence in $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$, then it is a Cauchy sequence for $(d_{\mathfrak{S}}, d_{\mathfrak{A}}, d_{\mathfrak{M}}, d_{\mathfrak{R}})$.

Theorem 3.15. For a $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S} (G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ the following conditions are equivalent.

- (1) $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ is complete.
- (2) A FP exists for each $(1)-K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G .
- (3) There is a FP for each $(1/2)-K_{\mathfrak{C}}$ on G .

Proof. By Theorem 3.9, (1) \implies (2).

It is also obvious that, (2) \implies (3).

(3) \implies (1). Let $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ be a fuzzy metric space that is neutrosophic. Make the assumption that $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$ is not complete. Then, in $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$, there is a Cauchy sequence $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ that does not converge in $\tau_{(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R})}$. Without sacrificing generality, assume that whenever $n \neq m$, $\rho_n \neq \rho_m$.

Take $C := \{\rho_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$. Then both C and all the sets of the form $C \setminus \{\sigma\}$, $y \in G$ are closed for $\tau_{(\mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R})}$.

Then by condition (iii) in Definition 2.13, for any $y \in G \setminus C$ it can be observed that,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) &> 0, \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) &< 1. \end{aligned}$$

It can be noted that the sets C and $C \setminus \{\sigma\}$ coincide in this case. Since by Definition 3.14, $(\rho_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is also a Cauchy sequence for semi-metrics $d_{\mathfrak{S}}, d_{\mathfrak{A}}, d_{\mathfrak{M}}, d_{\mathfrak{R}}$, $\exists n(\sigma) \in \mathbb{N}$ such that, $\forall j, k \geq n(\sigma)$,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}). \end{aligned}$$

However for any $\sigma \in C$, there exists $n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sigma := \rho_n$.

Also we have,

$$d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) > 0, \text{ and } d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) < 1.$$

Therefore, there exists $n(\sigma) > n$ such that, for any $j, k \geq n(\sigma)$,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}), \\ d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho_j, \rho_k) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}). \end{aligned}$$

Now we define a mapping $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ as follows:

$$\mathfrak{F}\sigma = x_{n(\sigma)}, \quad y \in G.$$

Then it is obvious that, \mathfrak{F} has no FPs (note that, to be specific, $\rho_n \neq x_{n(\sigma)}$, since $n(\sigma) > n$).

It now remains to show that, \mathfrak{F} is a $(1/2)-K_{\mathcal{C}}$ on $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$.

For this purpose, let $\sigma, w \in G$ such that $\forall \kappa > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \min \{ \mathfrak{S}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{S}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \min \{ \mathfrak{A}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{A}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) \} &> 1 - \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{M}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{M}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) \} &< \kappa, \\ \max \{ \mathfrak{R}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, \kappa), \mathfrak{R}(w, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa) \} &< \kappa. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore by Definition 3.14,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma), d_{\mathfrak{S}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) &< \kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma), d_{\mathfrak{A}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) &< \kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma), d_{\mathfrak{M}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) &> 1 - \kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma), d_{\mathfrak{R}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) &> 1 - \kappa. \end{aligned}$$

Now if $n(\sigma) < n(w)$, it is inferred that,

$$\begin{aligned} d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) = d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) < \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) = d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) &< \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) \\ &\leq \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) < \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) = d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) \\ &\geq 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\ d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) = d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) &> 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, C \setminus \{\sigma\}) \\ &\geq 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}\kappa. \end{aligned}$$

As a result by Definition 3.14,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7) &> 1 - \kappa/7, \\ \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7) &< \kappa/7. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, if $n(w) < n(\sigma)$, it is deduced that,

$$\begin{aligned}
 d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) &= d_{\mathfrak{S}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) < \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(w, C \setminus \{w\}) \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{S}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) < \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\
 d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) &= d_{\mathfrak{A}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) < \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(w, C \setminus \{w\}) \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{A}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) < \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\
 d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) &= d_{\mathfrak{M}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(w, C \setminus \{w\}) \\
 &\geq 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{M}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}\kappa, \\
 d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w) &= d_{\mathfrak{R}}(\rho_{n(\sigma)}, \rho_{n(w)}) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(w, C \setminus \{w\}) \\
 &\geq 1 - \frac{1}{7}d_{\mathfrak{R}}(w, \mathfrak{F}w) > 1 - \frac{1}{7}\kappa.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, by Definition 3.14,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathfrak{S}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7), \mathfrak{A}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7) &> 1 - \kappa/7, \\
 \mathfrak{M}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7), \mathfrak{R}(\mathfrak{F}\sigma, \mathfrak{F}w, \kappa/7) &< \kappa/7.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence \mathfrak{F} is a $(1/2)$ - $K_{\mathfrak{E}}$. This completes the proof. \square

To conclude this section, we will now demonstrate that Theorem 2.15 can be obtained by a similar methodology to the one given in [40] for Hu's theorem.

Let (G, d) be a metric space. Define $d_{1/2}$ a metric defined on G as follows:

$$d_{1/2}(\rho, \sigma) = \min \{1/2, d(\rho, \sigma)\} \quad \forall \rho, \sigma \in G$$

The topologies induced by d and $d_{1/2}$ can then be said to coincide. Additionally, if $(G, d_{1/2})$ is complete, then (G, d) is complete. It follows that $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ will be complete for every continuous t-norm and t-conorm, \star and \diamond , respectively, if $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \star, \diamond)$ is also complete (compare Example 2.12).

Proposition 3.16. [39] *A metric space (G, d) is given. Then, a $K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on $(G, d_{1/2})$ is also a $K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on (G, d) .*

Proposition 3.17. *Given a metric space (G, d) with $d(\rho, \sigma) \leq 1, \forall \rho, \sigma \in G$. Then for any continuous t-norm and t-conorm, \star and \diamond respectively, every $(1/2)$ - $K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ is a $K_{\mathfrak{E}}$ on (G, d) .*

Proof. Let $\mathfrak{F} : G \rightarrow G$ be a $(1/2)$ - $K_{\mathcal{E}}$ on $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$. We shall show that,

$$d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) \leq c[d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho) + d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma)], \quad \forall \rho, \sigma \in G, \text{ for some } c \in (0, 1/2).$$

In fact, let us assume the contrary. Then, $\exists \rho, \sigma \in G$ such that $d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) > c[d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho) + d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma)]$. Let $L = d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho) + d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma)$. Then $L \in [0, 2)$. Choose $\epsilon > 0$ such that $c(L + \epsilon) < 1$ and $d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) > c(L + \epsilon)$. Now since,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, L + \epsilon) &= \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, L + \epsilon) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, L + \epsilon) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, L + \epsilon) = 1, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, L + \epsilon) &= \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, L + \epsilon) = 0, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\rho, \mathfrak{F}\rho, L + \epsilon) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\sigma, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, L + \epsilon) = 0, \end{aligned}$$

and \mathfrak{F} is a $(1/2)$ - $K_{\mathcal{E}}$, it is deduced that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &> 1 - c(L + \epsilon) > 0, \\ \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &> 1 - c(L + \epsilon) > 0, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &< c(L + \epsilon) < 1, \\ \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &< c(L + \epsilon) < 1. \end{aligned}$$

However, on the other hand, from $d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma) > c(L + \epsilon)$, it can be inferred that,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &= \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) = 0, \\ \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) &= \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d(\mathfrak{F}\rho, \mathfrak{F}\sigma, c(L + \epsilon)) = 1. \end{aligned}$$

This is a contradiction. Hence the proof. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.16: Only the 'if' portion has been shown here. Assume that there is a FP for each $K_{\mathcal{E}}$ on (G, d) . On the $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ $(G, \mathfrak{S}, \mathfrak{A}, \mathfrak{M}, \mathfrak{R}, \star, \diamond)$, let F be a $(1/2)$ - $K_{\mathcal{E}}$. Given that $d_{1/2} \leq 1$, Proposition 3.16 implies that \mathfrak{F} is a $K_{\mathcal{E}}$ on $(G, d_{1/2})$; hence, Proposition 3.17 asserts that (G, d) is a $K_{\mathcal{E}}$. T has a FP as a result. Thus, according to Theorem 3.15, $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^{d_{1/2}}, \star, \diamond)$ is complete.

As a result, $(G, \mathfrak{S}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{A}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{M}_{01}^d, \mathfrak{R}_{01}^d, \star, \diamond)$ is complete, and hence, (G, d) .

4. Conclusion

This study proves important fixed-point results in the context of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$, such as the Banach fixed-point theorem, the Edelstein fixed-point theorem, and fixed-point results of the Kannan type. The completeness of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$ has been further characterized using the derived Kannan-type results. Furthermore, a number of fundamental ideas have been presented and thoroughly characterized in the context of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}S}$, including Cauchy sequences, convergence, completeness, and semi-metrics. These theoretical conclusions have been supported by a number of illustrative examples.

The results of this study have potential applications in various fields. In data science, they can be employed to design more robust clustering and classification algorithms under uncertainty and fuzziness. In engineering, these results can aid in the modeling and analysis of systems characterized by indeterminate or imprecise parameters, such as control systems or structural stability. In optimization, the findings provide a theoretical foundation for solving real-world problems involving vague or partial information, such as supply chain management, resource allocation, and scheduling. Furthermore, these results can be applied in medical diagnosis systems to enhance decision-making processes that involve uncertainty and ambiguity.

Looking ahead, the derived results could be extended to explore best proximity results in $NF_{\mathfrak{M}SS}$. Furthermore, the developed concepts have the potential for practical applications in optimization problems across various real-world scenarios. The framework could also be expanded to investigate other conventional fixed-point theorems, such as the Ćirić fixed-point theorem, Chatterjea fixed-point theorem, and Suzuki fixed-point theorem, within the realm of $NF_{\mathfrak{M}SS}$.

Funding: There was no outside funding for this research.

Acknowledgments: Contributors are thankful to the honorable reviewers for improvement of the article.

Conflicts of Interest: Contributors affirm that there are no known competing interests happening.

References

1. Brouwer, L. E. J. (1912). Über Abbildung von Mannigfaltigkeiten. *Mathematische Annalen*, 71, 97–115. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01456931>]
2. Banach, S. (1922). Sur les opérations dans les ensembles abstraits et leur application aux équations intégrales. *Fundamenta Mathematicae*, 133–181. [DOI: <http://eudml.org/doc/213289>]
3. Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Inf. Cont.*, 8, 338–353. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-9958\(65\)90241-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-9958(65)90241-X)]
4. Atanassov, K. (1986). Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Int. J. Bioautomation*, 20, 1. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114\(86\)80034-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114(86)80034-3)]
5. Smarandache, F. (1999). *A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic*. In *Philosophy* (pp. 1–141). American Research Press, USA.
6. Al-shami, T. M., & Mhemdi, A. (2023). Generalized frame for orthopair fuzzy sets: (m, n) -fuzzy sets and their applications to multi-criteria decision-making methods. *Information*, 14, 56. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/info14010056>]
7. Kramosil, I., & Michálek, J. (1975). Fuzzy metrics and statistical metric spaces. *Kybernetika*, 11, 336–344. [DOI: <http://eudml.org/doc/28711>]
8. George, A., & Veeramani, P. (1994). On some results in fuzzy metric spaces. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.*, 64, 395–399. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114\(94\)90162-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114(94)90162-7)]

9. Çoker, D. (1997). An introduction to intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.*, 88, 81–89. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114\(96\)00076-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-0114(96)00076-0)]
10. Park, J. H. (2004). Intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces. *Chaos Solitons Fractals*, 22, 1039–1046. [DOI: [doi: 10.1016/j.chaos.2004.02.051](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2004.02.051)]
11. Kaleva, O., & Seikkala, S. (1984). On fuzzy metric spaces. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.*, 12, 215–229. [DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114\(84\)90069-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0165-0114(84)90069-1)]
12. Smarandache, F. (2006). Neutrosophic set-a generalization of the intuitionistic fuzzy set. In *Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Granular Computing*. Atlanta, GA, USA.
13. Salama, A. A., & Alblowi, S. A. (2012). Neutrosophic set and neutrosophic topological spaces. *IOSR J. Math.*, 3, 31–35. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.9790/5728-0343135>]
14. Ejegwa, P. A., Akowe, S. O., Otene, P. M., & Ikyule, J. M. (2014). An overview on intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Int. J. Sci. Technol. Res.*, 3, 142–145.
15. Majumdar, P. (2015). Neutrosophic sets and its applications to decision making. In *Computational Intelligence for Big Data Analysis: Frontier Advances and Applications* (pp 97–115). Springer International Publishing, Cham, Switzerland.
16. Alaca, C., Turkoglu, D., & Yildiz, C. (2006). Fixed points in intuitionistic fuzzy metric spaces. *Chaos, Solitons Fractals*, 29, 1073–1078. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chaos.2005.08.066>]
17. Nădăban, S. (2016). Fuzzy b-metric spaces. *Int. J. Comput. Commun. Control.*, 11, 273–281. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15837/ijccc.2016.2.2443>]
18. Sonam, Bhardwaj, R., & Narayan, S. (2023). Fixed point results in soft fuzzy metric spaces. *Mathematics*, 11, 3189. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math11143189>]
19. Sonam. (2024). Some fixed point results in soft fuzzy metric spaces via altering soft distance. *Adv. Math. Sci. Appl.*, 33, 189–200. [DOI: <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:270228523>]
20. Gregori, V., Miñana, J. J., & Miravet, D. (2019). Fuzzy partial metric spaces. *Int. J. Gen. Syst.*, 48, 260–279. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/03081079.2018.1552687>]
21. Gregori, V., & Romaguera, S. (2004). Fuzzy quasi-metric spaces. *Appl. Gen. Topol.*, 5, 129–136. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4995/agt.2004.2001>]
22. Sonam, Rathore, V., Pal, A., Bhardwaj, R., & Narayan, S. (2023). Fixed-point results for mappings satisfying implicit relation in orthogonal fuzzy metric spaces. *Adv. Fuzzy Syst.*, 2023, 5037401. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/5037401>]
23. Zararsız, Z., & Riaz, M. (2022). Bipolar fuzzy metric spaces with application. *Comput. Appl. Math.*, 41, 49. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40314-021-01754-6>]
24. Vetro, C. (2011). Fixed points in weak non-Archimedean fuzzy metric spaces. *Fuzzy Sets Syst.*, 162, 84–90. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fss.2010.09.018>]
25. Sonam, Chauhan, C. S., Bharadwaj, R., & Narayan, S. (2023). Fixed point results in soft rectangular b-metric space. *Nonlinear Funct. Anal. Appl.*, 28, 753-774. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22771/nfaa.2023.28.03.11>]
26. Sonam, & Bhardwaj, R. (2024). Existence and uniqueness of solutions of nonlinear integral equations through results in fuzzy bipolar metric spaces. *J. Nonlinear Model. Anal.*, in press.
27. Broumi, S., Bakali, A. et. al. (2018). Neutrosophic sets: An overview. In *On Neutrosophic Theory and Applications II* (pp. 403–434). Pons Editions, Brussels, Belgium, EU. ISBN 978-1-59973-559-7
28. Jeyaraman, M., Jeyanthi, V., Mangayarkkarasi, A. N., & Smarandache, F. (2021). Some new structures in neutrosophic metric spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 42, 49–64. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4711499>]
29. Kirişçi, M., & Şimşek, N. (2020). Neutrosophic metric spaces. *Math. Sci.*, 14, 241–248. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1907.00798>]

30. Sowndrarajan, S., Jeyaraman, M., & Smarandache, F. (2020). Fixed point results for contraction theorems in neutrosophic metric spaces. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 36, 308-318. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4065458>]
31. Ishtiaq, U., Javed, K., Uddin, F., Sen, M. D. L., Ahmed, K., & Ali, M. U. (2021). Fixed point results in orthogonal neutrosophic metric spaces. *Complexity*, 2021, Article ID 2809657, 1-18. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/2809657>]
32. Asghar, A., Hussain, A., Ahmad, K., Ishtiaq, U., Sulami, H. A., & Hussain, N. (2023). On neutrosophic 2-metric spaces with application. *J. Funct. Spaces*, 2023, Article ID 9057107, 1-9. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9057107>]
33. Janardhanan, G., Mani, G., Ege, O., Varadharajan, V., & George, R. (2023). Orthogonal neutrosophic 2-metric spaces. *J. Inequal. Appl.*, 2023, 112. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13660-023-03024-x>]
34. Mani, G., Subbarayan, P., Mitrović, Z. D., Aloqaily, A., & Mlaiki, N. (2023). Solving some integral and fractional differential equations via neutrosophic pentagonal metric space. *Axioms*, 2, 758. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms12080758>]
35. Saeed, M., Ishtiaq, U., Kattan, D.A., Ahmad, K., & Sessa, S. (2023). New fixed point results in neutrosophic b-metric spaces with application. *Int. J. Anal. Appl.*, 21, 73-73. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.28924/2291-8639-21-2023-73>]
36. Das, S., Roy, B. K., Kar, M. B., Kar, S., & Pamučar, D. (2020). Neutrosophic fuzzy set and its application in decision making. *J. Ambient. Intell. Humaniz. Comput.*, 11, 5017-5029. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020-01808-3>]
37. Abbas, M., Ali, B., & Romaguera, S. (2014). On generalized soft equality and soft lattice structure. *Filomat*, 28, 1191-1203. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL1406191A>]
38. Ali, B., Saleem, N., Sundus, N., Khaleeq, S., Saeed, M., & George, R. (2022). A contribution to the theory of soft sets via generalized relaxed operations. *Mathematics*, 10, 2636. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math10152636>]
39. Romaguera, S. (2020). A fixed point theorem of Kannan type that characterizes fuzzy metric completeness. *Filomat*, 34(14), 4811-4819. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL2014811R>]
40. Romaguera, S., & Tirado, P. (2020). Characterizing complete fuzzy metric spaces via fixed point results. *Mathematics*, 8(2), 273. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/math8020273>]
41. Kannan, R. (1968). Some results on fixed points. *Bull. Calcutta. Math. Soc.*, 68, 71-76.
42. Reich, S. (1971). Kannan's fixed point theorem. *Boll. Un. Math. Ital.*, 4, 1-11.
43. Subrahmanyam, P. V. (1975). Completeness and fixed-points. *Mh. Math.*, 80, 325-330. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01472580>]
44. Ghosh, S., Sonam, Bhardwaj, R., & Narayan, S. (2024). On neutrosophic fuzzy metric space and its topological properties. *Symmetry*, 16(5), 613. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym16050613>]
45. Ghosh, S., Sonam, Sarkar, D., Halder, P., & Bhardwaj, R. (2024). An application of invariant point theory in G-metric spaces with special emphasis on alpha-psi contraction. *Math. Model. Comp. Appl.*, 207-217. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781394248438.ch12>]
46. Ghosh, S., Bhardwaj, R., Narayan, S., & Sarkar, D. (2025). A result concerning best proximity point from the perspective of G-metric spaces using control functions with an application. *Adv. Math. Sci. Appl.*, 34(1), 33-46 (*in press*).
47. Halder, P., Ghosh, S., Bhardwaj, R., Sonam, & Narayan, S. (2024). Fixed point results for compatible mapping of type (α) in fuzzy metric spaces. *Math. Model. Comp. Appl.*, 219-230. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781394248438.ch13>]

48. Saleem, N., Ishtiaq, U., Ahmad, K., Sessa, S., & Martino, D. F. (2023). Fixed point results in neutrosophic rectangular extended b-metric spaces. *Neutrosophic Systems with Applications*, 9, 48–80. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.61356/j.nswa.2023.63>]
49. Sahin, M., & Kargin, A. (2021). Neutrosophic triplet v-generalized metric space. *Axioms*, 7(3), 67. [DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/axioms7030067>]

Received: Sep 2, 2024. Accepted: Feb 10, 2025